

Impact of Advertisement on Consumer Behavior on College Students

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Abstract

The purpose of present study is to analysis the impact of advertisement on consumer behavior on college students. This paper aims to explore the role of advertisement on attitudes towards buying behavior. The sample data has been collected from college students, between 18-26 age groups. As a whole seven brands of body and detergent soaps has been taken into consideration. Data collection was made in respect of their co-relations with advertisements.

Introduction

Advertising is a growing business in India today. It has been gaining importance in its economy. The significance of advertising continues to increase year by year. The host of new products marketed, the expenses and the risks involved in launching them, and the low cost of personal selling are among the conditions which have placed a heavy responsibility on the advertising industry. In India, with its growing productive capacity and output, there is a need for finding consumers for this growing output, and advertising plays an important role in the process of moving the goods from the producers to the consumers. Advertising helps to increase mass marketing while aiding the consumer to choices and preferences from amongst the variety of products offered for his selection and option. We are all influenced with advertisements in our day to day life. Its forms and contents both are well liked amongst consumers.

Understanding Consumer Behavior

Consumer buying behavior is the study of how people buy, what they buy, when they buy and why they buy. It blends elements from psychology, sociology, anthropology and economics. It attempts to understand the buyer decision-making process, both individually and in groups. It studies features of individual consumer such as demographics, psychographics, and behavioral variables in an effort to understand people's wants. It also tries to measure influences on the consumer from groups such as family, friends, reference groups, and society in general. The study and knowledge of consumer buying behavior helps to firms to decide their marketing strategies

and product offerings. The decision to buy milk, bread, a cake, personal computer and a new car all are very different. Expensive purchases are likely to involve more buyer deliberation and more participants.

Objective of the Study

1. To study consumers' buying behavior on consumer.
2. To explore the impact of personality used in advertisements on consumer Behavior.
3. To find out the acceptance of advertisement due to appeal used in it.

Past Studies

Amit Kumar (2011) in his paper 'Celebrity Endorsements and its impact on consumer buying behavior' focuses on the perception of Indian consumers about celebrity endorsements, the celebrity attributes likely to influence consumer purchase intentions. The practice of celebrity endorsements has proliferated over time. Now days it has become a pervasive element of advertising industry especially in India. Celebrity endorsement business has become a multi-million industry in India. Marketers use celebrity endorsers to influence the purchase decision of consumers in order to increase their sales and extend their market shares. This made the author curious to explore the impact of celebrity endorsements on consumer buying behavior.

Aneza Bashir and Najma Iqbal Malik (2009), concluded in their study, "Effect of advertisement on consumer behavior of university students" that advertisement persuades the consumer to at least buy the product once in a life time. Personality used in commercials influenced the consumers more as compare to keyword/caption. Results also revealed that consumers considered advertisement as a reliable source of knowledge as compare to others (friends, neighbors, reference group) opinions.

Scope of the Study

The present study helps in exploring the impact of advertisement on customer behavior, it is understood that advertisement is not only use for awareness about the product and services it also play an important role in brand emotion, selection option and preference towards the products and also sales of the products.

Need of the Study

It is a matter of fact that all the companies spend a lot of money on advertisements to establish the product in market as well as brands. It is also important for companies to know whether their advertisements are effective or not.

Sample Size

A sample of "150" students was taken for the purpose of study and analysis. The sample size consist age group of 18 to 26 years. They all were viewer's of electronic advertising.

Sampling Technique

Convenience sampling technique (non probability sampling) was used for the survey. Questionnaire filled by the selected customers.

Data Collection

The data was collected through primary and secondary sources.

1. Primary data: primary data was collected with the help of well structured questionnaires and schedules administered among 150 respondents.
2. Secondary data: Secondary data will be obtained from various published reports, research studies, bulletin, Government's publications etc.

Tools and Techniques

Present research is based on quantitative descriptive approach, so it requires statistical treatment of the data. Different tools and techniques will be used to analyze the data, collected through well structured questionnaire and schedule. The tools were used in Percentage, Gatt’s Ranking Technique and Correlation.

Period of the Study

The data collected from May 2018 to July 2018 (Three months)

Data Analysis

Table 1 Gender & Education Wise Claification

Sl. No	Gender	UG	PG	Total	Percentage
1	Male	55(60)	32(55)	87	58
2	Female	37(40)	26(45)	63	42
	Total	92	58	150	100

Source: Primary Source

The table1 clearly indicates that 58percent of college students belonged to male and the remaining 42 percent of the students belonged to female category.

Table 2 Different Type of Advertisement Factors Influencing Purchase of the Brand

Sl. No	Factors	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Television	42	28.00
2	News paper	31	20.67
3	Magazines	14	09.33
4	Internet	17	11.33
5	Wall writing	08	05.33
6	Radio	26	17.34
7	Others	12	08.00
	Total	150	100.00

Source: Primary Source

From the above table 2, it is clear that out of 150 respondents, 28 percentages are accepted that TV is the most striking media to advertise for the products .

Table 3 Factors Effecting Consumers’ Buying Decision

Sl.No	Factors	Total Score	Avg. Score	Rank
1	Advertisements & sales Promotion	7398	49.33	IV
2	Price, Discount & Offer	7844	52.30	II
3	Quality & Quantity	7555	50.36	III
4	Income	7318	48.78	V
5	Social Status	8290	55.26	I
6	Packing	7238	48.25	VI
7	Festival Season	7225	48.16	VII
8	Goodwill	7130	47.53	VIII

Source: Primary Source

It is observed from the table3 that majority of the respondents have opined that giving Social Status is the buying decision factor for college students continue the buying in a particular brand hence it is ranked first. This is followed by providing Price, discount and offer, Quality and quantity, Advertisements and sales promotion and Income Where ranked Second, Third rank and so on. Packing, Festival Season, and goodwill hence it ranked sixth, Seventh and Eighth respectively.

Table 4 Frequency and Percentages of Factors Influencing Purchase of the Brand

Sl.No	Factors	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Owen Decision	35	23.33
2	Doctors	22	14.67
3	Advertisements	47	31.33
4	Friends/Relatives	28	18.67
5	Others	18	12.00
	Total	150	100.00

Source: Primary Source

Table 4 is exploring that the role which advertisements play cannot be neglected. According to study it is found that advertisements influence the consumers a great deal in selecting soaps. Next come Owen decision that is the consumer himself and then comes the role of family/Relatives and doctor. At many times someone’s reference also helps in selecting a brand.

Table 5 Frequency and Percentages of Persuasion Due to Advertisement

Sl. No	Response category	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Mostly Persuaded	62	41.34
2	Sometimes Persuaded	53	35.34
3	Never Persuaded	35	23.32
	Total	150	100.00

Source: Primary Source

Table 5 understood that the three basic things in advertisement that can influence the viewers were personality showed that almost 35.34-41.34 percentage respondents were persuaded to purchase the product due to advertisement, whereas 23.32 percentage respondents were never persuaded.

Table 6 Frequency and Percentages of Impact of Appeal in Advertisement on Consumer Behavior

Sl. No	Response Category	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Mostly Persuaded	57	38
2	Sometimes Persuaded	48	32
3	Never Persuaded	45	30
	Total	150	100

Source: Primary Source

Table 6 showed that 38 percentages of the respondents were mostly influenced by the appeal and 32 percentages were sometime influenced by appeal in the advertisement whereas 30 percentages of respondents were never influenced from the appeal used in advertisement, which means that advertisement did affect consumer behavior to a greater extent. But to find out whether its effectiveness motivates them to purchase the product at once or not further analyses were done.

Table 7 Frequency and Percentages of Impact of Personality on Consumers' Buying Behavior

Sl. No.	Response category	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Mostly Persuaded	69	46.00
2	Sometimes Persuaded	44	29.34
3	Never Persuaded	37	24.66
	Total	150	100.00

Source: Primary Source

The table 7 reveals that another most persuasive component of advertisement was personality. Impact of personality used in commercial was also explored 49 percentage of the consumers were mostly influenced by the personality used in advertisement of specific brand. But 24.66 percentage consumers were never influenced by personality used in commercials.

Table 8 Frequency and Percentages of Impact of Keyword / Caption or Slogan on Consumers' Buying Behavior

Sl.No.	Response Category	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Mostly Persuaded	49	32.67
2	Sometimes Persuaded	67	44.67
3	Never Persuaded	34	22.66.
	Total	150	100.00

Source: Primary Source

The table 8 indicated that only 32.67 - 44.67 percentages of consumers were influenced by keyword/ caption/slogan used in advertisement of specific brand whereas 22.67 percentage had no influence of keyword / caption.

Table 9 Relationship Between Effectiveness of Appeal and Purchasing Pattern

Sl.No.	Appeal Immediate Purchase	Mostly	Some time	Never	Total
1	Yes	30	28	12	70
2	No	25	35	20	80
	Total	55	63	32	150

Source: Primary Source

It is inferred from the table 9 that the calculate value (0.6856) that there was effectiveness of appeal and purchasing pattern Moderate levels of Positive of correlation in this under the study.

Table 10 Relationships Between Persuasion and Keyword/ Caption of Advertisement

Sl.No.	Appeal Immediate Purchase	Mostly	Some time	Never	Total
1	Yes	23	26	13	62
2	No	24	31	33	54
	Total	47	57	46	150

Source: Primary Source

It is clear from the table 10 that the calculate value (0.4922) that there was persuasion and keyword/caption of advertisement Moderate levels of Positive of correlation in this under the study.

Table 11 Brand Preference of Consumers (Body Soaps)

Sl.No.	Brand	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Pears	21	14.00
2	Lux	24	16.00
3	Hamam	31	20.66
4	Chinthoal	18	12.00
5	Lifebuoy	25	16.66
6	Nature Power	14	09.34
7	Mysore sandal	17	11.34
	Total	150	100.00

Source: Primary Source

From the table 11 it has been observed that 20.66 percent of respondents are used hamam, followed by 16.66, percentage are used in lifebuoy, 16 percentage are used in lux. The reaming of respondents are chinthol(12), Mysore sandal(11.34) and power (9,34), to be buying the body soap respectively under the study area.

Table 12 Brand Preference of Consumers (Detergent Soaps)

Sl.No.	Brand	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Rin	27	18.00
2	Arasan	17	11.33
3	Ponvandu	24	16.00
4	Surf Excel	23	15.33
5	Power	29	19.34
6	Tide	12	08.00
7	Others	18	12.00
	Total	150	100.00

Source: Primary Source

From the table 12 it has been observed that 19.34 percent of respondents are used Power, followed by 18, percentage are used in Rin, 16 percentage are used in ponvandu. The reaming of respondents are Surf excel (15.33), Arasan(11.33) and Tide (8), to be buying the body detergent soaps respectively under the study area.

Conclusion

It has been concluded that advertising have great impact on buying behavior of customers. Before purchasing any product customers or consumers collect information for their proper purchasing decision making activities. Hence advertising is mostly adapted to get information about the products. There are different factors influenced on buying behavior of consumers. It can be presumed that repeated advertisement on selected channels on prim time will unknowingly influence the purchase decision. It has been also concluded that maximum no.of consumers are attracted towards the advertising on purchasing of the products.

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